

MODIFIED CROP COEFFICIENTS FOR PIGEON PEA AT AKOLA STATION

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Abstract

The study focuses on the normalization of crop coefficients (K_c) for pigeon pea at Akola Station, using the FAO Penman-Monteith method to determine the reference evapotranspiration (E_{To}). Pigeon pea, a significant crop in the Vidarbha region, requires precise water management due to its extended growth period. The research modifies the FAO K_c values to reflect local climatic conditions, considering factors such as relative humidity, wind speed, and plant height. The K_c values for the initial, mid-season, and end stages of pigeon pea were found to be 0.50, 1.08, and 0.74, respectively. These modified coefficients provide a more accurate estimation of water requirements, enabling better irrigation management and promoting sustainable agricultural practices in the region. The results highlight the variation between the standard FAO K_c values and those adjusted for Akola's local conditions, emphasizing the importance of region-specific data in agricultural water management. This research offers valuable insights for farmers, researchers, and policymakers in optimizing water use and enhancing crop productivity for pigeon pea in the Vidarbha region.

Keywords: Crop coefficients, Pigeon pea, Reference evapotranspiration, FAO Penman Monteith method, etc.

Introduction:

Pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan*), commonly known as "tur" or "arhar" in India, holds significant importance in the agricultural landscape of the Vidarbha region. This leguminous crop is valued for its multifaceted contributions to the local economy, food security, and sustainable agriculture. Pigeon pea cultivation serves as a source of income for numerous farmers in the Vidarbha region. Its demand in domestic and international markets ensures a steady market for the crop. Farmers rely on the income generated from pigeon pea sales to support their families and invest in other agricultural activities.

Water management for long-duration crops like pigeon pea requires careful planning and execution due to the extended growth period and varying water requirements throughout the crop's lifecycle. By implementing effective water management strategies tailored to the prolonged growth cycle of pigeon pea crops, farmers can achieve better yields, conserve water resources, and promote sustainable agricultural practices in the region. Determining crop water requirements is of paramount importance in efficient and sustainable agricultural practices. Proper water management ensures that crops receive the right amount of water at the right time, optimizing growth, yield, and resource utilization.

Crop water requirement is the amount of water that a crop needs to grow, develop, and produce optimal yields under specific environmental conditions. It is a crucial factor in agricultural water management, as providing the right amount of water at the right time is essential for achieving efficient water use, minimizing waste, and maximizing crop productivity. Certainly, the concept of evapotranspiration (E_{Tc}) as a ratio of reference evapotranspiration (E_{To}) and crop coefficient (K_c) is a fundamental approach used to estimate the water requirement of a specific crop. The formula for calculating crop evapotranspiration (E_{Tc}) is:

$$E_{Tc} = E_{To} \times K_c$$

where:

E_{Tc} = Crop evapotranspiration (mm)

E_{To} = Reference evapotranspiration (mm)

K_c = Crop coefficient (dimensionless), representing the growth and water use of the crop at a specific growth stage.

Reference Evapotranspiration (E_{To}) is a standardized measure of the rate at which water is lost from a well-maintained, green, grass-covered surface under specific meteorological conditions. It serves as a baseline or reference point for estimating the water needs of different crops and vegetation. The concept of the crop coefficient acknowledges that different crops have varying rates of water consumption based on their growth characteristics, leaf area, canopy cover, and other factors. By adjusting the reference evapotranspiration with the appropriate crop coefficient, one can calculate the actual water requirement of specific crop under given conditions. Proper irrigation

management guided by accurate crop water demand contributes to higher crop yields. This translates into increased income for farmers, improving their economic well-being and encouraging sustainable farming practices.

As a study area, Akola district provides opportunity for research and analysis on themes like as water resources, water use efficiency of major crops grown in Vidarbha, and identifying solutions to improve water usage while optimizing agricultural productivity. Therefore, the present study was carried out to determine crop coefficient values by modifying the FAO crop coefficients for local climatic conditions for pigeon pea at Akola.

Materials And Methods:**Details of study area**

Akola is in the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra, India. It falls in latitudes 20.7°N to 21.1°N and longitudes 76.5°E to 77.2°E. Soils of Akola are predominantly black cotton soils; these soils belong to the Vertisols group, having a high percentage of clay with fine-grained texture and moderate to high water-holding capacity. Monsoon arrives in June and lasts until September, providing the majority of the annual rainfall. Winters are relatively mild and dry.

Data Collection

Daily meteorological data were downscaled and downloaded for the period 1992 - 2021 (30 years) for Akola station from website (power.larc.nasa.gov) of The POWER Project supported by NASA Earth Science for prediction of worldwide energy resources. Data pertaining to maximum temperature (°C) at 2 m (T_{max}), minimum temperature (°C) at 2 m (T_{min}), relative humidity (%) at 2 m (RH), wind speed (ms^{-1}) at 2 m (WS) and all sky surface shortwave downward irradiance ($MJ\ m^{-2}\ day^{-1}$) i.e. Solar radiation (R_s) are available free to download from that website and data of these parameters was downloaded. Then, mean weekly averages of all above meteorological data was determined, by averaging it, according to standard meteorological weeks. Other parameters like geographic locations viz., latitude, longitude and altitude were also obtained.

Determination of Reference Crop Evapotranspiration (E_{To})

The weekly reference evapotranspiration for Akola was calculated by converting daily climatic data into weekly values based on standard meteorological weeks (SMW). The FAO Penman-Monteith method was used to estimate weekly reference evapotranspiration (E_{To} , $mm\ day^{-1}$) at the Akola station. The mathematical expression for FAO Penman Monteith method to estimate the reference evapotranspiration (E_{To}) is as follows;

$$E_{To} = \frac{[0.408 \Delta (R_n - G) + \gamma \left(\frac{900}{T+273} \right) u_2 (e_s - e_a)]}{[\Delta + \gamma (1 + 0.34u_2)]}$$

where,

ET_o -Reference Evapotranspiration (mm day⁻¹)
 Δ -Slope of saturation vapour curve (kPa °C⁻¹)
R_n -Net radiation at the crop surface (MJ m⁻² day⁻¹)
G -Soil heat flux density (MJ m⁻² day⁻¹)
 γ -Psychrometric constant (kPa °C⁻¹)
T -Mean air temperature (°C)
u₂ -Wind speed at 2.0 m height (ms⁻¹)
e_a -Actual vapour pressure (kPa)
e_s -Saturation vapour pressure (kPa)
(e_s - e_a) - Saturation vapour pressure deficit (kPa)
Estimated weekly reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_o) over 30 years (1992-2021) was then averaged to get the average weekly ET_o for 52 standard meteorological weeks for Akola station.

Determination of modified crop coefficients:

The procedure involves modifying the FAO crop coefficients based on factors such as local evapotranspiration rates, relative humidity, wind speed, and plant height. Here is a breakdown of the key points:

Identifying Crop Growth Stages and Determining Crop Coefficients

Growth Stages Identification:

The growth stages of pigeon pea (initial, crop development, mid-season, and late/end-season) were identified based on previous field studies in the region.

Kc Initial (Kc ini) Calculation:

The Kc initial value was derived from the FAO Irrigation and Drainage Paper No. 56 using the graphical method. The wetting event for Kc initial was determined by considering the general irrigation intervals during the Kharif season for pigeon pea to identify the initial crop coefficient value.

Kc Mid (Kc mid) and Kc End (Kc end) Calculation:

These values were adjusted for local climatic conditions, considering daily minimum relative humidity, wind speed, and plant height. The equations used for adjustment:

$$Kc_{mid} = Kc_{mid(FAO)} + [0.04(u_2 - 2) - 0.004(RH_{min} - 45)] (h/3)^{0.3}$$

where,

Kc_{mid(FAO)} - Value for Kc mid taken from FAO-56,

Table 1. Average Weekly Reference Evapotranspiration for Akola (mm/day)

SMW	ET _o (mm/day)	SMW	ET _o (mm/day)	SMW	ET _o (mm/day)
1	3.7	19	10.4	37	3.7
2	3.9	20	10.8	38	3.6
3	4.3	21	11.2	39	3.9
4	4.5	22	10.3	40	3.9
5	4.8	23	8.6	41	3.9
6	5.2	24	6.8	42	3.7
7	5.6	25	5.7	43	3.8
8	5.9	26	5.2	44	3.8
9	6.2	27	4.7	45	3.6
10	6.3	28	4.3	46	3.5
11	6.6	29	3.9	47	3.5
12	7.3	30	3.7	48	3.4
13	7.7	31	3.5	49	3.5
14	8.0	32	3.5	50	3.5
15	8.2	33	3.6	51	3.6
16	8.9	34	3.5	52	3.7
17	9.3	35	3.4		
18	10.1	36	3.5		

Table 1 shows the mean weekly reference evapotranspiration value for Akola station. The ET_o was highest during the month of May whereas it was lowest during the month of August. It may be due to the highest temperature during the month of May in summer season as compared to August in monsoon season. The peak value of reference evapotranspiration for Akola station was found to be 11.2 mm/day in SMW 21 whereas the lowest ET_o of 3.4 mm/day were found for SMW 35.

u₂ - Mean value for daily wind speed at 2 m height (m/s), (0.70)
RH_{min} - Mean value for daily minimum relative humidity during the mid-season growth stage (%),
h - Mean plant height during the mid-season stage (m)

$$Kc_{End} = Kc_{End(FAO)} + [0.04(u_2 - 2) - 0.004(RH_{min} - 45)] (h/3)^{0.3}$$

where,

Kc_{end(FAO)} -Value for Kc end taken from FAO-56,

u₂ - Mean value for daily wind speed at 2 m height (m/s),

RH_{min} - Mean value for daily minimum relative humidity during the end-season growth stage (%),

h - Mean plant height during the end-season stage (m)

Constructing the Crop Coefficient Curve

The growing period was divided into four distinct growth stages (initial, crop development, mid-season, and late/end-season). The lengths of these stages and the corresponding Kc values (Kc ini, Kc mid, Kc end) were identified. A curve was constructed by connecting straight line segments through each growth stage. Horizontal lines were drawn for Kc ini in the initial stage and Kc mid in the mid-season stage. Diagonal lines connected Kc ini to Kc mid during the crop development stage and Kc mid to Kc end during the late season stage. After plotting, a best-fitting soft curve was manually drawn for the entire growing season. Weekly Kc values were then read from the curve, and daily Kc values were averaged to obtain modified weekly crop coefficients. The obtained weekly Kc values for pigeon pea were plotted against crop weeks in Microsoft Excel to determine the daily values of crop coefficient by obtaining curve fitting equation. Then estimated daily Kc values were averaged to get modified weekly and stage wise crop coefficients more exactly.

Results And Discussion

Determination of Reference crop evapotranspiration:

Estimated average weekly reference evapotranspiration series for the period of 30 years (1992-2021) is presented in Table 1 for Akola.

Determination of modified crop coefficients

The initial, mid, and end-stage crop coefficient (Kc) values for pigeon pea at Akola station were determined using FAO guidelines, with values of 0.51, 1.06, and 0.52, respectively. The initial Kc was derived using the FAO graphical method and 6-day wetting intervals, while Kc mid and Kc end were calculated using FAO formulas that consider local climate factors like wind speed, relative humidity, and plant height. These Kc values were then plotted to construct a curve, from which weekly Kc values were manually extracted. Finally, the weekly

Kc values were normalized and fitted with a curve in Excel to obtain daily Kc values for the growing season. The polynomial equation 4

was obtained for best curve for FAO modified Kc value for pigeon pea is as follows;

$$Kc_t = 6.3079 \left(\frac{t}{T}\right)^4 - 15.341 \left(\frac{t}{T}\right)^3 + 9.6189 \left(\frac{t}{T}\right)^2 - 0.5745 \left(\frac{t}{T}\right) + 0.4895$$

Where, Kc_t = Crop coefficient of tth day, t = Day considered and T = Total period of crop growth from sowing to harvesting (days).

Figure 1. Modified weekly crop coefficients obtained for pigeon pea vs t/T

Then estimated daily Kc values were averaged to get weekly normalized and modified crop coefficients more precisely. The obtained daily kc values for pigeon pea were again averaged to get crop growth stage wise Kc values according to their length of growing stages, i.e. initial, development, mid-season, and end stage. Determined crop coefficient values were found as 0.50, 0.78, 1.08 and 0.74 for initial (24 days), development (52 days), midseason (58 days)

and end (46 days) stages of pigeon pea crop respectively. Whereas the standard crop coefficient values provided by FAO are 0.40, 1.15 and 0.55 for initial, midseason and end stage of pigeon pea.

The modified weekly crop coefficient values obtained after normalizing the Kc values over the growing period for pigeon pea at Akola station are shown in table 2.

Table 2. Modified Crop Coefficient values for pigeon pea at Akola station

Crop Week	Days (t)	Total Days (T)	t/T	Modified Kc values (after normalizing using poly. equation)
1	0	180	0.00	0.48
2	7	180	0.04	0.49
3	14	180	0.08	0.51
4	21	180	0.12	0.56
5	28	180	0.16	0.61
6	35	180	0.19	0.67
7	42	180	0.23	0.74
8	49	180	0.27	0.81
9	56	180	0.31	0.88
10	63	180	0.35	0.94
11	70	180	0.39	0.99
12	77	180	0.43	1.04
13	84	180	0.47	1.07
14	91	180	0.51	1.10
15	98	180	0.54	1.11
16	105	180	0.58	1.11
17	112	180	0.62	1.10
18	119	180	0.66	1.07
19	126	180	0.70	1.03
20	133	180	0.74	0.98
21	140	180	0.78	0.91
22	147	180	0.82	0.84
23	154	180	0.86	0.76
24	160	180	0.89	0.66
25	166	180	0.92	0.57
26	172	180	0.96	0.51
27	178	180	0.99	0.51
28	180	180	1.00	0.50

Conclusion

The variation in standard crop coefficients provided by FAO and the modified Kc values can be clearly seen for pigeon pea at local climatic conditions of Akola. The obtained crop coefficients values and the

values of reference evapotranspiration can be used to calculate accurate crop water requirement for pigeon pea crop for the region by farmers, researchers and policy makers in making informed decisions to ensure

that crops receive the right amount of water for achieving sustainable and productive agriculture.

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